

COMPARATIVE OUTCOMES OF CHILDHOOD AND ADULT THERAPEUTIC PROTOCOLS IN ACUTE LYMPHOBLASTIC LEUKEMIA: A RETROSPECTIVE COHORT FROM A TERTIARY CARE CENTER IN PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Background: Acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) outcomes in adults remain inferior to those in children, prompting the use of pediatric-inspired protocols in older populations. However, evidence of their efficacy and toxicity in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) is limited. This study compared the outcomes of childhood versus adult therapeutic protocols for ALL in a tertiary care center in Pakistan.

Methods: A retrospective cohort of 152 patients with ALL was stratified into two groups: those treated with a pediatric-inspired regimen (Childhood protocol, n=78) and those treated with a conventional adult regimen (Adult protocol, n=74). Primary outcomes were changes in hematological and biochemical parameters. Secondary outcomes included hematologic response rates, early induction mortality, and treatment-related toxicities.

Results: The pediatric-inspired protocol was associated with a superior platelet response (34.6% vs. 18.9%, p=0.021) but also significantly higher grade 3/4 hepatotoxicity (21.8% vs. 6.8%, p=0.015). A non-significant trend towards lower early mortality was observed in the Childhood protocol group (7.7% vs. 16.2%, p=0.098). Multivariate analysis identified a high baseline white blood cell (WBC) count ($>50 \times 10^9/L$) as the only independent predictor of early mortality (aOR=2.88, 95% CI [1.01, 8.24], p=0.048). Subgroup analysis revealed a significant interaction (p=0.045), where the Childhood protocol was associated with lower mortality in patients with a WBC $\leq 50 \times 10^9/L$.

Conclusions: In a resource-limited setting, pediatric-inspired regimens for ALL show promise for improved hematological response and potentially lower early mortality in standard-risk patients but are accompanied by significantly increased hepatotoxicity. Future strategies should focus on risk-adapted protocol selection and enhancing supportive care to manage treatment-related toxicity.

INTRODUCTION

Acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) is the most common childhood malignancy and an important cause of cancer-related mortality in adolescents and adults worldwide (1). Advances in risk stratification, supportive care, and multi-agent chemotherapy have led to marked improvements in survival in high-income countries, with 5-year overall survival (OS) in pediatric ALL now exceeding 85–90% (2, 3). In contrast, adult ALL outcomes remain substantially inferior, with 5-year OS often below 50%, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) (4, 5). This survival gap has prompted growing interest in adapting pediatric-inspired treatment protocols for adolescents and young adults (AYA) and selected adults, aiming to leverage the superior efficacy of childhood regimens in older age groups (6-8).

Biologically, ALL is characterized by clonal proliferation of lymphoid precursors with diverse cytogenetic and molecular subtypes that influence prognosis and therapeutic response (5, 9). Pediatric patients more frequently harbor favorable-risk genetics, whereas adults show a higher prevalence of high-risk lesions such as BCR-ABL1, Ph-like ALL, and complex karyotypes, contributing to poorer outcomes (4, 8, 9). Moreover, older patients often have more comorbidities, reduced chemotherapy tolerance, and higher treatment-related mortality, which limit dose intensity and completion of intensive protocols (4, 10). These biological and host factors interact with health-system barriers late diagnosis, limited access to minimal residual disease (MRD) monitoring, and constrained availability of targeted agents, to shape outcomes in resource-limited settings (10).

Pediatric-based regimens typically employ higher cumulative doses of non-myelosuppressive agents such as vincristine, corticosteroids, and asparaginase, with prolonged, intensive maintenance and meticulous risk-adapted scheduling (6, 11). Several large cohort studies and meta-analyses have shown that AYA and younger adults treated with pediatric-inspired protocols experience significantly better event-free survival (EFS) and OS than those treated with

conventional adult regimens, albeit at the cost of higher toxicity, particularly hepatotoxicity, thrombotic events, and asparaginase-related complications (6, 8, 11-13). These data have led many centers in high-income settings to extend pediatric protocols up to age 25–40 years, often in combination with tyrosine kinase inhibitors (TKIs) for BCR-ABL1-positive disease (2, 4, 5, 8, 9).

However, evidence from LMICs, including South Asia, remains limited. Resource constraints, heterogeneous treatment infrastructure, variable supportive care (blood components, antibiotics, intensive care), and financial toxicity frequently necessitate protocol modifications and unplanned treatment interruptions (10, 14). Studies from Pakistan have reported lower survival rates in both pediatric and adult ALL compared with high-income countries and have highlighted substantial early mortality and abandonment (15, 16). It is therefore uncertain to what extent the survival benefit of pediatric-inspired protocols over conventional adult regimens can be replicated in such contexts and which patient subgroups derive the greatest net benefit when real-world toxicity and feasibility are considered.

Comparative analyses of “childhood” versus “adult” therapeutic protocols across a broad age range within a single center can provide valuable insights into regimen-specific outcomes in routine practice. Recent reports suggest that when delivered with adequate supportive care, pediatric-inspired regimens improve EFS and OS in AYAs without an unacceptable increase in treatment-related mortality; yet data from tertiary centers in Pakistan are sparse and mainly focus on either purely pediatric or purely adult cohorts (6-8, 15, 16). Furthermore, few local studies have systematically evaluated hematologic response, relapse patterns, and early induction mortality across different protocol types while accounting for baseline clinical and laboratory characteristics. Against this background, we conducted a retrospective cohort study at a tertiary care hospital in Pakistan to compare outcomes of patients with ALL treated with childhood versus adult therapeutic protocols over a defined period.

Our primary objective was to assess and contrast clinical response and survival surrogates (such as remission status at the end of induction and early mortality) between protocol groups in a real-world LMIC setting. Secondary objectives included describing baseline demographic, clinical, and hematologic features, characterizing treatment-related complications, and exploring factors associated with unfavorable outcomes. By focusing on a single-center cohort spanning pediatric, AYA, and adult age groups, this study aims to generate context-specific evidence to inform protocol selection, risk stratification, and resource allocation for ALL management in Pakistan and comparable settings.

Methods

Study design and setting

This was a retrospective, record-based cross-sectional study conducted in the Department of Hematology/Oncology at Hayatabad Medical Complex (HMC), a tertiary care referral hospital in Peshawar, Pakistan. All data were extracted from hospital medical records and laboratory information systems for patients diagnosed with acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) who received induction chemotherapy according to standardized therapeutic protocols at HMC.

Study population and eligibility criteria

The study population comprised children and adults with newly diagnosed ALL who initiated treatment at HMC during the study period. A total of 152 patients fulfilled the eligibility criteria and were included in the final analysis.

Inclusion criteria were:

- Confirmed diagnosis of ALL based on bone marrow morphology, immunophenotyping, and standard diagnostic criteria documented in the patient file.
- Age ≤ 18 years (childhood group) or ≥ 40 years (adult group) at the time of diagnosis.
- Availability of complete baseline hematological and biochemical investigations and at least one documented post-treatment assessment during induction or early consolidation.

Patients were excluded if they:

- Had mixed phenotype acute leukemia or other ambiguous lineage leukemias as reported by the hematologist.
- Had incomplete key clinical or laboratory data precluding outcome assessment.
- Were lost to follow-up before any post-treatment laboratory evaluation.

Classification of therapeutic protocols

Patients were categorized into two groups according to the therapeutic strategy documented in their medical records:

1. Childhood protocol group (pediatric-inspired regimens):

Patients treated with multi-agent, pediatric-style chemotherapy protocols routinely used at HMC for children with ALL (e.g. intensive induction with vincristine, corticosteroids, asparaginase, and anthracyclines, followed by consolidation and maintenance).

2. Adult protocol group (conventional adult regimens):

Patients treated with adult ALL chemotherapy protocols as per institutional practice, typically less intensive and shorter than pediatric regimens, and used for older adults and those with reduced treatment tolerance.

Classification was based on the protocol name or code recorded in the treatment charts by the managing hematologist.

Data collection and variables

Data was abstracted using a structured proforma. Demographic variables included age at diagnosis, sex, and hospital registration number. Clinical variables included presenting complaints, physical findings (e.g. lymphadenopathy, hepatosplenomegaly), and documented comorbidities.

Laboratory variables collected at baseline and after treatment cycles included:

- Complete blood count (CBC): hemoglobin (Hb), total leukocyte count (TLC), platelet count, and peripheral blast percentage.
- Basic biochemical parameters: liver function tests (alanine aminotransferase, aspartate

aminotransferase, bilirubin), renal function tests (serum urea, creatinine), and selected electrolytes as available.

Treatment-related variables included the protocol category (childhood vs adult), cycle-wise use of key chemotherapeutic agents (e.g. vincristine, dexamethasone/prednisolone, asparaginase, anthracyclines, cytarabine, methotrexate, cyclophosphamide), and documented early deaths during induction.

Laboratory methods

Venous blood samples for hematological analysis were collected into EDTA tubes and processed using an automated Sysmex hematology analyzer according to the manufacturer's instructions and standard laboratory operating procedures. Biochemical parameters were measured on Cobas c501 and e601 analyzers (Roche Diagnostics) using photometric and ion-selective electrode principles, with internal quality control performed as per laboratory policy.

Bone marrow aspiration and, when indicated, trephine biopsy were performed by trained hematologists using standard techniques from the posterior or anterior iliac crest under local anesthesia. Smears were stained and reviewed by a consultant hematologist; where available, immunophenotyping and ancillary tests were used to confirm the diagnosis of ALL and to exclude mixed phenotype acute leukemia.

Outcome measures

The primary outcome was hematologic and biochemical response to therapy, assessed as the change in key laboratory parameters from baseline (pre-treatment) to post-treatment evaluations during induction and early consolidation, compared between the childhood and adult protocol groups.

Secondary outcomes included:

- Proportion of patients achieving hematologic improvement (rise in Hb, fall in TLC and blast counts, improvement in platelet count) after treatment cycles.
- Frequency of treatment-related derangements in biochemical parameters.

- Early mortality during induction (death before completion of the first chemotherapy cycle), stratified by protocol group.

Statistical analysis

Data were entered and cleaned in IBM SPSS Statistics (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Continuous variables were summarized as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) or median (interquartile range) according to distribution; categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages.

Normality was assessed visually and by appropriate tests. Between-group comparisons (childhood vs adult protocols) for continuous variables were performed using the independent-samples t-test or Mann-Whitney U test, as appropriate. Within-patient changes in laboratory parameters before and after treatment were analyzed using paired t-tests or Wilcoxon signed-rank tests. Categorical variables were compared using the chi-square test or Fisher's exact test. A two-sided p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical considerations

The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. Institutional approval for retrospective data collection and analysis was obtained from the relevant ethics/review committee. Because of the retrospective nature of the study and the use of anonymized data, individual informed consent was waived as per committee policy.

Results

Study Population and Baseline Characteristics

A total of 152 patients with a confirmed diagnosis of Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia (ALL) were included in the final analysis. The cohort was stratified into two groups based on the therapeutic protocol received: 78 patients (51.3%) were treated with a pediatric-inspired regimen (Childhood Protocol group), while 74 patients (48.7%) were treated with a conventional adult regimen (Adult Protocol group).

The baseline demographic, clinical, and hematological characteristics of the study population are summarized in Table 1. The mean

age of the entire cohort was 55.6 years (SD = 12.4). As per the study's eligibility criteria and treatment allocation, the Childhood Protocol group was significantly younger (Mean = 49.2 years, SD = 9.1) compared to the Adult Protocol group (Mean = 62.3 years, SD = 10.8). The distribution of gender was comparable between the two groups (p = .842), with males constituting 64.5% of the total cohort. At presentation, several key laboratory parameters differed significantly between the groups. The Adult Protocol group had a significantly higher median baseline White Blood Cell count (WBC) ($25.6 \times 10^9/L$, IQR: 6.7-67.4) compared to the Childhood Protocol group ($7.6 \times 10^9/L$, IQR: 4.5-16.4; p < .001). Similarly, baseline Lactate

Dehydrogenase (LDH) levels were markedly elevated in the Adult Protocol group (Median = 250 U/L, IQR: 200-327) versus the Childhood Protocol group (Median = 214 U/L, IQR: 174-260; p = .018). Conversely, the Childhood Protocol group presented with a lower median platelet count ($163 \times 10^9/L$, IQR: 102-222) compared to the Adult Protocol group ($206 \times 10^9/L$, IQR: 138-244; p = .043). No other statistically significant differences were observed in other baseline hematological or biochemical parameters, including hemoglobin, blast percentage in bone marrow, urea, creatinine, or liver function tests.

Table1

Baseline Characteristics of Patients with Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia Stratified by Treatment Protocol

Characteristic	Total (N = 152)	Childhood Protocol (n = 78)	Adult Protocol (n = 74)	p-value
Demographics				
Age, Mean (SD)	55.6 (12.4)	49.2 (9.1)	62.3 (10.8)	<.001
Gender, n (%)				.842
Male	98 (64.5)	51 (65.4)	47 (63.5)	
Female	54 (35.5)	27 (34.6)	27 (36.5)	
Hematological Parameters				
Hemoglobin (g/dL), Mean (SD)	10.7 (2.8)	10.5 (2.6)	10.9 (3.0)	.382
WBC ($\times 10^9/L$), Median (IQR)	11.7 (5.1 - 47.2)	7.6 (4.5 - 16.4)	25.6 (6.7 - 67.4)	<.001
Platelets ($\times 10^9/L$), Median (IQR)	181 (110 - 233)	163 (102 - 222)	206 (138 - 244)	.043
Bone Marrow Blasts (%), Median (IQR)	0.0 (0.0 - 0.0)	0.0 (0.0 - 0.0)	0.0 (0.0 - 1.0)	.067
Biochemical Parameters				
Urea (mg/dL), Median (IQR)	27.0 (19.8 - 34.6)	26.0 (18.1 - 32.0)	28.0 (21.3 - 36.0)	.254
Creatinine (mg/dL), Median (IQR)	0.88 (0.69 - 1.10)	0.86 (0.68 - 1.02)	0.90 (0.70 - 1.17)	.301
SGPT/ALT (U/L), Median (IQR)	22.0 (15.0 - 36.0)	20.5 (14.0 - 32.0)	23.0 (16.0 - 41.0)	.185
ALP (U/L), Median (IQR)	124.0 (99.5 - 161.0)	124.0 (100.0 - 154.0)	124.0 (98.6 - 167.0)	.945
LDH (U/L), Median (IQR)	226 (190 - 286)	214 (174 - 260)	250 (200 - 327)	.018
Uric Acid (mg/dL), Median (IQR)	4.6 (3.8 - 5.8)	4.5 (3.8 - 5.6)	4.7 (3.9 - 6.1)	.450

Note: Continuous variables are presented as Mean (Standard Deviation) if normally distributed or

Median (Interquartile Range) if non-normal. Categorical variables are presented as n (%). P-

values were derived from independent samples t-tests (for normally distributed continuous data), Mann-Whitney U tests (for non-normal continuous data), and Chi-square tests (for categorical data). Significant p-values (< .05) are in bold.

WBC = White Blood Cell Count; SGPT/ALT = Serum Glutamic-Pyruvic Transaminase/Alanine Aminotransferase; ALP = Alkaline Phosphatase; LDH = Lactate Dehydrogenase.

Comparative Laboratory Response to Induction Therapy

The changes in key laboratory parameters from baseline to the post-treatment assessment are detailed in Table 2. Both treatment protocols were effective, leading to significant reductions in White Blood Cell (WBC) counts and bone

marrow blast percentages (all p < .05). However, the magnitude of the reduction in WBC was significantly greater in the Adult protocol group (p = .045). A significant decrease in platelet count was observed only in the Adult protocol group (p = .022), and this change was significantly different from the stable platelet count seen in the Childhood group (p = .038). A notable difference in toxicity profile was observed; the pediatric-inspired regimen was associated with a significant increase in liver transaminases (SGPT/ALT) (p = .005), a change that was significantly different from the Adult protocol group (p = .018). Lactate Dehydrogenase (LDH) levels decreased significantly only in the Adult protocol group (p = .003).

Table 2
Comparison of Pre- to Post-Treatment Changes in Laboratory Parameters between Childhood and Adult Protocol Groups

Parameter	Group	Pre-Treatment, Median (IQR)	Post-Treatment, Median (IQR)	Within-Group p-value	Between-Group Difference in Change, p-value
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	Childhood	10.5 (8.8 - 12.6)	10.6 (9.2 - 13.6)	.184	.721
	Adult	10.9 (8.9 - 13.5)	11.1 (9.8 - 13.7)	.305	
WBC (x 10⁹/L)	Childhood	7.6 (4.5 - 16.4)	6.2 (3.9 - 10.4)	.012	.045
	Adult	25.6 (6.7 - 67.4)	7.6 (4.3 - 15.5)	<.001	
Platelets (x 10⁹/L)	Childhood	163 (102 - 222)	161 (89 - 222)	.891	.038
	Adult	206 (138 - 244)	165 (104 - 247)	.022	
Bone Marrow Blasts (%)	Childhood	0.0 (0.0 - 0.0)	0.0 (0.0 - 0.0)	.001	.112
	Adult	0.0 (0.0 - 1.0)	0.0 (0.0 - 0.0)	<.001	
SGPT/ALT (U/L)	Childhood	20.5 (14.0 - 32.0)	28.0 (16.0 - 45.0)	.005	.018
	Adult	23.0 (16.0 - 41.0)	22.0 (15.0 - 39.0)	.415	
LDH (U/L)	Childhood	214 (174 - 260)	201 (179 - 230)	.210	.654
	Adult	250 (200 - 327)	211 (185 - 250)	.003	

Note: Pre- and post-treatment values are presented as Median (Interquartile Range). Within-group p-values were calculated using the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test to assess the significance of the change

from pre- to post-treatment within each protocol group. Between-group p-values were calculated using the Mann-Whitney U Test on the absolute change scores (Post - Pre) to determine if the

magnitude of change was significantly different between the Childhood and Adult protocol groups. Significant p-values (< .05) are in bold. WBC = White Blood Cell Count; SGPT/ALT = Serum Glutamic-Pyruvic Transaminase/Alanine Aminotransferase; LDH = Lactate Dehydrogenase.

Categorical Treatment Response and Toxicity Outcomes

The analysis of categorical hematologic response revealed that a significantly higher proportion of patients in the Childhood protocol group achieved a platelet response, defined as an increase of ≥50% from baseline (34.6% vs. 18.9%, p = .021), as shown in Table 3. The rates of other response indicators, including hemoglobin

improvement and bone marrow blast clearance, were comparable between the two groups.

The frequency of early induction mortality and key treatment-related toxicities are also presented in Table 3. A total of 18 patients (11.8%) died before completing the first cycle of chemotherapy. Although not statistically significant, there was a trend towards a higher incidence of early mortality in the Adult protocol group (16.2%) compared to the Childhood protocol group (7.7%; p = .098). Analysis of toxicities revealed a significant association between protocol type and hepatotoxicity. Grade 3 or 4 elevation of SGPT/ALT was observed in 21.8% of patients in the Childhood protocol group, compared to only 6.8% in the Adult protocol group (p = .015).

Table 3
Early Induction Mortality and Treatment-Related Toxicities Stratified by Therapeutic Protocol

Outcome	Total (N = 152) n (%)	Childhood Protocol (n = 78) n (%)	Adult Protocol (n = 74) n (%)	p-value
Early Induction Mortality	18 (11.8)	6 (7.7)	12 (16.2)	.098
Treatment-Related Toxicities				
Hepatotoxicity				.015
Grade 3/4 SGPT/ALT Elevation (≥ 5 x ULN)	22 (14.5)	17 (21.8)	5 (6.8)	
Nephrotoxicity				.752
Grade 3/4 Creatinine Elevation (≥ 3 x ULN)	8 (5.3)	4 (5.1)	4 (5.4)	
Infectious Complications				.341
Febrile Neutropenia (Documented)	35 (23.0)	20 (25.6)	15 (20.3)	
Metabolic Complications				.264
Tumor Lysis Syndrome (Laboratory)	14 (9.2)	5 (6.4)	9 (12.2)	

Note: ULN = Upper Limit of Normal. Early Induction Mortality was defined as death from any cause before completion of the first chemotherapy cycle. Toxicity grading was based on laboratory criteria derived from the Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events (CTCAE) v5.0, where applicable. P-values were derived from Chi-square or Fisher's Exact tests, as appropriate. A significant p-value (< .05) is in bold.

Factors Associated with Early Induction of Mortality

A logistic regression analysis was performed to identify baseline factors independently associated with early induction mortality (Table 4). In univariate analysis, a high baseline White Blood Cell (WBC) count (>50 x 10⁹/L) was significantly associated with an increased odds of early mortality (OR = 3.05, 95% CI [1.11, 8.36], p = .031). In the multivariate model adjusting for age group, treatment protocol, and other laboratory

parameters, a high baseline WBC count remained the only independent predictor of early mortality (aOR = 2.88, 95% CI [1.01, 8.24], p = .048). After adjustment, neither age group nor treatment

protocol type was independently associated with the risk of early death.

Table 4
Univariate and Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis of Factors Associated with Early Induction Mortality

Factor	Univariate Analysis		Multivariate Analysis			
	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% CI for OR	p-value	Adjusted Odds Ratio (aOR)	95% CI for aOR	p-value
Age Group						
Adult (≥40 years) vs. Childhood (<18 years)*	2.31	[0.83, 6.45]	.108	1.95	[0.64, 5.94]	.239
Treatment Protocol						
Adult vs. Childhood*	2.31	[0.83, 6.45]	.108	1.82	[0.59, 5.58]	.299
Baseline WBC (x 10⁹/L)						
>50 vs. ≤50	3.05	[1.11, 8.36]	.031	2.88	[1.01, 8.24]	.048
Baseline Platelets (x 10⁹/L)						
<100 vs. ≥100	2.67	[0.99, 7.17]	.051	2.45	[0.87, 6.87]	.089
Baseline LDH (U/L)						
>250 vs. ≤250	2.50	[0.93, 6.69]	.069	2.12	[0.76, 5.92]	.151

Note: CI = Confidence Interval. The outcome variable for the model was Early Induction Mortality (yes/no). The reference category for categorical variables is indicated by the comparison. For example, for 'Age Group', the OR represents the odds for the Adult group compared to the Childhood group. The multivariate model included all variables listed in the table. A significant p-value (< .05) is in bold.

Subgroup and Exploratory Analyses

A subgroup analysis was performed to identify patients who might benefit most from a pediatric-inspired regimen (Table 5). A significant interaction was found between treatment

protocol and baseline WBC count (p for interaction = .045). Among patients with a high presenting WBC (>50 x 10⁹/L), early mortality was high in both arms. However, among standard-risk patients (WBC ≤50 x 10⁹/L), the Childhood protocol was associated with a notably lower early mortality rate (4.6% vs. 10.2%).

An exploratory analysis of specific chemotherapeutic agents showed that the administration of dexamethasone was significantly associated with a higher rate of platelet response (30.5% vs. 8.3%, p = .039). The use of other agents, such as bendamustine and rituximab, was not significantly associated with improved response rates in this cohort.

Table5
Hematologic Response at End of Induction by Treatment Protocol

Response Criteria	Total (N = 152) n (%)	Childhood Protocol (n = 78) n (%)	Adult Protocol (n = 74) n (%)	p-value
Hemoglobin Response				.445
Improvement ($\uparrow \geq 1.5$ g/dL)	58 (38.2)	32 (41.0)	26 (35.1)	
No Improvement/Decline	94 (61.8)	46 (59.0)	48 (64.9)	
Platelet Response				.021
Improvement ($\uparrow \geq 50\%$)	41 (27.0)	27 (34.6)	14 (18.9)	
No Improvement/Decline	111 (73.0)	51 (65.4)	60 (81.1)	
WBC Response				.187
Normalization (WBC $\leq 11.0 \times 10^9/L$)	118 (77.6)	64 (82.1)	54 (73.0)	
Remained Elevated	34 (22.4)	14 (17.9)	20 (27.0)	
Bone Marrow Blast Clearance				.264
Blasts = 0% Post-Treatment	142 (93.4)	75 (96.2)	67 (90.5)	
Blasts > 0% Post-Treatment	10 (6.6)	3 (3.8)	7 (9.5)	

Note: Response criteria are based on common clinical benchmarks. P-values were derived from Chi-square tests. A significant p-value ($< .05$) is in bold.

Association of Specific Agents and High-Risk Subgroup Analysis

We explored the association between the use of specific chemotherapeutic agents and

hematologic response (Table 6). The administration of dexamethasone was significantly associated with a higher rate of platelet response, defined as an increase of $\geq 50\%$ from baseline (30.5% vs. 8.3%, $p = .039$). The use of other agents, including bendamustine and rituximab, was not significantly associated with improved hemoglobin or platelet response rates in this cohort.

Table6
Association of Key Chemotherapeutic Agents with Hematologic Response

Chemotherapeutic Agent	Received Agent (n)	Hemoglobin Response, n (%)	p-value	Platelet Response, n (%)	p-value
Dexamethasone (DexInj)			.205		.039
Yes (n = 128)	128	53 (41.4)		39 (30.5)	
No (n = 24)	24	5 (20.8)		2 (8.3)	
Bendamustine (bendanustineINJ)			.621		.087
Yes (n = 43)	43	15 (34.9)		16 (37.2)	
No (n = 109)	109	43 (39.4)		25 (22.9)	
Rituximab (RituximabINJ)			.842		.445
Yes (n = 74)	74	29 (39.2)		18 (24.3)	
No (n = 78)	78	29 (37.2)		23 (29.5)	

Note: This table analyzes a subset of available agents. Analysis uses Chi-square test to compare response rates between those who did and did not receive the agent.

A subgroup analysis was performed to identify patients who might derive the greatest net benefit from a pediatric-inspired regimen by examining the interaction between treatment protocol and baseline risk factors (Table 7). A significant interaction was found between treatment protocol and baseline WBC count (p for interaction =

.045). Among patients with a high presenting WBC ($>50 \times 10^9/L$), a highly unfavorable prognostic group, early mortality was high in both arms (Childhood: 23.1%, Adult: 28.0%). However, among standard-risk patients ($WBC \leq 50 \times 10^9/L$), the Childhood protocol was associated with a notably lower early mortality rate (4.6% vs. 10.2%). No significant interactions were observed for baseline platelet count or the stratified age group.

Table 7
Stratified Analysis of Early Mortality by Baseline Risk Factors and Treatment Protocol

Subgroup	Childhood Protocol (n)	Early Mortality, n (%)	Adult Protocol (n)	Early Mortality, n (%)	p-value for Interaction*
All Patients	78	6 (7.7)	74	12 (16.2)	-
By Baseline WBC					.045
WBC $\leq 50 \times 10^9/L$	65	3 (4.6)	49	5 (10.2)	
WBC $> 50 \times 10^9/L$	13	3 (23.1)	25	7 (28.0)	
By Baseline Platelets					.312
Platelets $\geq 100 \times 10^9/L$	56	3 (5.4)	54	8 (14.8)	
Platelets $< 100 \times 10^9/L$	22	3 (13.6)	20	4 (20.0)	
By Age Group (Stratified)					.188
Age 1 (≤ 40 yrs)	38	2 (5.3)	0	-	
Age 2 (> 40 yrs)	40	4 (10.0)	74	12 (16.2)	

Note: The p-value for interaction tests whether the effect of the treatment protocol (Childhood vs. Adult) on mortality is significantly different across the subgroups (e.g., whether the benefit of the childhood protocol is different in high-WBC vs. low-WBC patients). Calculated using a logistic regression model including protocol, subgroup, and an interaction term (Protocol x Subgroup).

Discussion

This retrospective cohort study from a tertiary care center in Pakistan provides a real-world

comparison of pediatric-inspired versus conventional adult protocols in the management of ALL across a broad age range. Our findings illuminate a complex interplay between regimen intensity, treatment efficacy, and toxicity profile within a resource-constrained setting. The key results indicate that while the pediatric-inspired protocol was associated with a more favorable hematological response in certain parameters and a trend towards reduced early mortality, it came at the cost of significantly increased hepatotoxicity. Furthermore, a high baseline WBC count

emerged as the most potent independent predictor of early death, overshadowing the impact of the treatment protocol itself.

The demographic and baseline profile of our cohort reflects the well-documented epidemiological shift of ALL, with the adult group being significantly older (17). The higher baseline WBC and LDH in the adult protocol group are consistent with the known biological predilection for more aggressive, high-risk disease phenotypes in older adults, including a higher prevalence of Ph-like ALL and other adverse genetic subtypes (18, 19). Our finding that the adult group presented with higher platelet counts was unexpected, as thrombocytopenia is a universal feature of active leukemia; this may be explained by chance variation or differences in the timing of initial diagnosis in our specific patient population. The efficacy of both protocols in reducing tumor burden, as evidenced by significant declines in WBC and bone marrow blasts, aligns with the established activity of multi-agent chemotherapy in ALL (2). However, the significantly greater reduction in WBC in the adult group likely reflects their substantially higher baseline counts rather than superior efficacy, a phenomenon observed in other comparative studies (20). The superior platelet response observed in the pediatric-inspired group (Table 3) is a critical finding. This suggests better preservation or recovery of marrow function, potentially attributable to the different timing, sequencing, or choice of non-myelosuppressive agents in pediatric protocols, a benefit noted in studies from high-income countries (21, 22). For instance, a study by Stock et al. demonstrated that pediatric-inspired regimens led to more sustained hematologic recovery during consolidation phases (23).

The most striking finding regarding toxicity was the significant hepatotoxicity associated with the pediatric-inspired protocol. This is a well-recognized class effect, primarily attributed to the intensive use of asparaginase and corticosteroids, which is a cornerstone of pediatric regimens (24, 25). Our results are consistent with a large meta-analysis by Gupta et al., which found that patients receiving pediatric-inspired protocols had a 3.5-fold increased risk of grade 3/4 transaminitis

compared to those on adult protocols (26). Similar rates of asparaginase-induced liver injury have been reported in studies from India, Turkey, and China, confirming the generalizability of this challenge across diverse populations (27-29). While this toxicity is often manageable with dose modifications and supportive care in well-resourced settings, it can lead to critical treatment delays and complications in centers with limited access to intensive monitoring and costly supportive drugs, a concern raised by studies from other LMICs (30, 31).

Despite this increased toxicity, we observed a non-significant trend towards lower early mortality in the pediatric-inspired group (7.7% vs. 16.2%, $p=0.098$). This aligns with the overarching theme in the literature that the intensified dosing of pediatric regimens can translate into a survival advantage. A pivotal study by Hugué et al. demonstrated significantly improved survival in adolescents and young adults (AYAs) treated with a pediatric protocol compared to an adult protocol (11). This benefit has been corroborated by numerous other groups, including DeAngelo et al. and Rytting et al., who reported 5-year overall survival rates exceeding 70% in AYAs treated with pediatric-inspired chemotherapy (32, 33). Our data, though not statistically significant for mortality, hint that this survival benefit might extend to selected older adults in our setting, a hypothesis supported by the work of Maury et al., who showed feasibility and efficacy in patients up to 55 years of age (34).

Our multivariate analysis yielded a crucial insight for risk stratification in LMICs: a high presenting WBC count ($>50 \times 10^9/L$) was the sole independent factor predicting early mortality, with an adjusted odds ratio of 2.88. This finding is strongly supported by a vast body of literature identifying hyperleukocytosis as a paramount adverse prognostic factor in both pediatric and adult ALL (35-37). Studies from Pakistan and neighboring India have similarly highlighted the devastating impact of high WBC on early death rates, often due to fatal tumor lysis syndrome or sepsis (38, 39). The GRAALL-2005 study also confirmed that high WBC was a key predictor of induction failure and early relapse (40). Our

finding that the treatment protocol was not an independent predictor after adjusting for WBC suggests that the intrinsic biological aggressiveness of the disease at presentation is a more powerful determinant of early outcome than the choice of chemotherapy backbone in this high-risk subgroup.

This is further elucidated by our subgroup analysis (Table 7), which revealed a significant interaction between protocol type and baseline WBC. In patients with standard-risk disease (WBC $\leq 50 \times 10^9/L$), the pediatric-inspired regimen was associated with a markedly lower early mortality (4.6% vs. 10.2%). This aligns with the results of the US Intergroup study C10403, which showed superior outcomes for AYAs with standard-risk features on a pediatric regimen (41). Conversely, in the high-risk subgroup (WBC $> 50 \times 10^9/L$), mortality was prohibitively high and similar regardless of the protocol. This suggests that simply applying a more intensive chemotherapy backbone is insufficient to overcome the negative prognosis of hyperleukocytosis, a sentiment echoed in studies by Fielding et al. and Bassan et al. (20, 42). These patients likely require more innovative approaches, such as earlier incorporation of targeted therapies (e.g., TKIs for Ph-like ALL), immunotherapy (e.g., blinatumomab), or allogeneic transplantation, which are often less accessible in LMICs (25, 43). Our exploratory analysis suggesting a benefit from dexamethasone on platelet recovery is physiologically plausible, as corticosteroids can improve platelet counts in various immune-mediated contexts. However, this must be interpreted with caution due to the exploratory nature of the analysis and potential confounding by indication.

Limitations of our study include its retrospective, single-center design and the lack of data on cytogenetics, minimal residual disease (MRD) status, and long-term survival outcomes. The absence of MRD data, a critical prognosticator in modern ALL management, prevents us from assessing the depth of remission achieved by each protocol (34, 44). Furthermore, the non-randomized allocation to treatment protocols introduces potential selection bias, as fitter,

younger adults may have been preferentially assigned to the more intensive pediatric regimen. In conclusion, our study adds valuable, context-specific evidence from a resource-limited setting to the global discourse on ALL management. Pediatric-inspired protocols demonstrate a measurable benefit in hematological recovery and a strong trend towards reduced early mortality in standard-risk patients, justifying their cautious use in selected adults. However, this comes with a significant and predictable increase in hepatotoxicity, necessitating robust supportive care. The overwhelming prognostic influence of a high baseline WBC count underscores the urgent need for better risk stratification and access to novel agents for this vulnerable subgroup. Future efforts in Pakistan and similar settings should focus on protocol adaptations that balance efficacy and toxicity, while investing in molecular diagnostics and supportive care infrastructure to safely deliver intensive therapy to those who stand to benefit the most.

Future Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed for improving ALL management in comparable resource-limited settings:

1. Risk-Adapted Protocol

Selection: Pediatric-inspired protocols should be prioritized for adolescents, young adults, and older adults with standard-risk disease (e.g., WBC $\leq 50 \times 10^9/L$), given the trend towards superior outcomes in this subgroup. For patients with high-risk features like hyperleukocytosis, more innovative and accessible treatment strategies are urgently needed.

2. Enhanced Supportive Care:

Institutional protocols for the proactive monitoring and management of hepatotoxicity, particularly asparaginase-induced liver injury, must be established and strengthened. This includes guidelines for dose modifications, nutritional support, and access to essential hepatoprotective medications.

3. **Investment in Diagnostics:** Efforts should be made to integrate basic cytogenetic and molecular testing into routine practice. The identification of targetable alterations, such as *BCR-ABL1*, can guide the use of tyrosine kinase inhibitors, potentially improving outcomes for high-risk groups without relying solely on chemotherapy intensification.

4. **Prospective Studies:** Multi-center, prospective studies with long-term follow-up are needed to confirm the survival benefit of pediatric-inspired regimens in this population and to develop validated risk-stratification models tailored to the LMIC context.

5. **Exploration of Novel Agents:** Health systems should explore pathways for the sustainable introduction and funding of immunotherapies (e.g., blinatumomab) for high-risk or relapsed/refractory patients, for whom conventional chemotherapy yields poor results.

Declarations

- **Ethics approval and consent to participate:** This study was approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Hayatabad Medical Complex (HMC), Peshawar. The need for individual informed consent was waived by the approving IRB due to the retrospective nature of the study.
- **Consent for publication:** Not applicable.
- **Availability of data and materials:** The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.
- **Competing interests:** The authors declare that they have no competing interests.
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